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Crisis management of hotel enterprises in Ukraine based on scenario planning

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Abstract. The study's relevance is determined by the need to enhance the resilience of hotel enterprises in Ukraine to destabilizing factors by implementing adaptive management strategies. In the context of economic disruptions, military actions, and shifts in consumer segments, applying forecasting methods becomes essential to ensure operational continuity. Scenario-based methods not only allow for assessing the potential impact of external threats but also enable the adaptation of managerial decisions to changing market conditions. The **article aims** to substantiate approaches to integrating scenario-based methods into the management system of hotel enterprises, considering the specifics of the Ukrainian market. **Methods.** A systems analysis was used to identify key threats and assess their impact on business operations. Structural and functional analysis was used to determine the main components of management strategies, their flexibility, and effectiveness in conditions of uncertainty. Both methods contributed to a comprehensive assessment of factors affecting operational activities and the development of practical recommendations for adaptation. **Results.** The study demonstrated that scenario-based methods facilitate timely responses to external changes, optimize management strategies, and mitigate the impact of destabilizing factors. The developed scenarios

consider regional specificities, resource constraints, and potential changes in consumer segments, contributing to greater flexibility in managerial decisions. It was found that the main barriers to implementing predictive methods include limited access to relevant data, an insufficient methodological framework, and a low level of digital competence among managers. Using digital platforms to monitor market changes enables timely adjustment of scenarios and prevents potential losses. **Conclusions.** The feasibility of integrating digital tools for situational monitoring, strategic adaptation, and personnel training has been substantiated. The application of adaptive methods enhances the ability of enterprises to respond quickly to external risks. Further research prospects include the development of models for evaluating the effectiveness of scenario-based methods and integrating machine learning algorithms for market data analysis.

Keywords: scenario forecasting, managerial decisions, crisis conditions, adaptive strategies, business resilience.

Антикризове управління готельними підприємствами України на основі сценарного планування

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Анотація. Актуальність дослідження зумовлено необхідністю підвищення стійкості готельних підприємств України до дестабілізаційних чинників шляхом впровадження адаптивних стратегій управління. В умовах економічних потрясінь, воєнних дій та змін у споживчих сегментах доцільним є застосування методів прогнозування, що дають змогу не лише оцінити ймовірні наслідки зовнішніх загроз, але й адаптувати управлінські рішення до

мінливих умов ринку, забезпечуючи безперервність операційної діяльності. **Метою** статті є обґрунтування практик інтеграції сценарних методів у систему управління готельними підприємствами з урахуванням специфіки українського ринку. **Методи.** Для досягнення мети було використано системний аналіз для виявлення ключових загроз та оцінки їх впливу на бізнес-операції. Структурно-функціональний аналіз застосовано для визначення основних складових стратегій управління, їх гнучкості та ефективності в умовах невизначеності. Обидва методи сприяли комплексній оцінці факторів, що впливають на оперативну діяльність, і розробці практичних рекомендацій щодо адаптації. **Результати.** Встановлено, що застосування сценарних методів сприяє своєчасному реагуванню на зміни у зовнішньому середовищі, оптимізації управлінських стратегій та зниженню впливу деструктивних чинників. Розроблені підходи мають враховувати регіональну специфіку, ресурсні обмеження та потенційні зміни у клієнтських сегментах, що підвищує гнучкість управлінських рішень. Виявлено, що серед основних перешкод для впровадження прогностичних методик – обмеженість доступу до релевантних даних, недостатня методологічна база та низький рівень цифрової підготовки управлінців. Використання цифрових платформ для моніторингу ринкових змін дає змогу своєчасно коригувати сценарії та запобігати втратам. **Висновки.** Обґрунтовано доцільність інтеграції цифрових інструментів для моніторингу ситуацій, адаптації управлінських стратегій та підвищення кваліфікації персоналу. Застосування адаптивних методик розширює можливості підприємств до швидкого реагування на зовнішні ризики. Перспективи подальших досліджень передбачають розроблення моделей оцінки ефективності сценарних методів та інтеграцію алгоритмів машинного навчання для аналізу ринкових даних.

Ключові слова: сценарне прогнозування, управлінські рішення, кризові ситуації, адаптивні стратегії, стійкість бізнесу.

Problem statement. In the conditions of an unstable economic environment and unpredictable external factors affecting the activities of hotel enterprises in Ukraine, the issue of anti-crisis management is becoming particularly relevant. The urgent need to develop and implement effective crisis management strategies is due to increased competition, fluctuations in demand, changes in consumer behavior, and a decrease in tourist flows. An important aspect in ensuring the sustainability of hotel enterprises is the use of forecasting methods that allow modeling possible scenarios and assessing their impact on the organization's activities, analyzing potential risks, and adapting management decisions to changing market conditions. In modern conditions, anti-crisis management should focus on the integration of flexible planning methods that take into account the specifics of the hotel business, the impact of external shocks, and potential threats to operational activities. The scientific significance of the study lies in identifying effective scenario planning models that can minimize the negative impact of crisis events on hotel enterprises, contribute to maintaining competitive advantages, and ensure sustainable development of the industry. The practical significance of the work is due to the development of recommendations for the formation of adaptive management strategies based on the identification of possible scenarios of events and the corresponding correction of the organizational structure of enterprises. The main task of the study is to analyze modern scenario planning practices in the hotel business, assess their effectiveness in crises, and develop proposals for improving anti-crisis management strategies, taking into account the specifics of the Ukrainian market.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Modern research on the anti-crisis management of hotel enterprises in Ukraine based on scenario planning indicates the presence of four main content areas.

The first area covers the theoretical foundations and concepts of anti-crisis management in the hotel business. Researchers L. V. Tiesheva, and V. O. Khtominska [1] explore the concept of Talent Management as a means of adapting

hotel enterprises to difficult conditions, focusing on strategic personnel management. Scientists V. Samodai, S. Rybalchenko, and Ye. Oryshchenko [2] analyze the management mechanisms of hotel sector enterprises during martial law, emphasizing the importance of forecasting for the prompt adjustment of management decisions. Researcher H. V. Kish [3] proposes measures to maintain hotel stability, considering the conditions of martial law. Authors L. Lipych, O. Khilukha, M. Kushnir, and I. Matviichuk [4] focus on improving management systems integrating innovative planning practices. Scientists V. Humeniuk, N. Kazuka, T. Malaniuk, I. Vivsiuk, and A. Betlei [5] analyze the international experience of ensuring the sustainability of the hotel business in conditions of uncertainty. Further research should be directed towards the integrated strategies for enterprises of different regions and scales.

The second direction concerns strategic planning and modeling of anti-crisis solutions. Authors O. Roik, and D. Zanevych [6] investigate the theoretical and methodological principles of managing tourism enterprises during socio-economic shocks, focusing on forecasting methods adaptation in Ukrainian realities. Researcher S. Arlou [7] analyzes the features of responding to external challenges in tourism, emphasizing the integration of long-term management practices. Scientists F. Seyitoğlu, and C. Costa [8] conduct a systematic review of forecasting methods in the hotel business, proposing new risk assessment practices. Scientists M. A. Köseoglu, H. E. Arici, M. Yeşiltaş, and L. Altınay [9] investigate the process of forming management strategies with an emphasis on testing the effectiveness of selected scenarios. Authors M. V. Harasymluk, A. B. Nahuliak, and Yu. T. Trots [10] substantiates ways to improve management decisions in the tourism business through communication strategies. Further research should focus on developing scenario models for risk management in conditions of war and economic instability.

The third direction covers practical aspects of implementing management strategies in the hotel business. Scientists F. Tjong, E. Goh, and V. Wilk [11] investigate the features of training managers to work in unpredictable situations,

emphasizing the need for long-term planning during the COVID-19 pandemic. Researchers D. Dimitrios, C. Christos, I. Ioannis, and L. Vasiliadis [12] focus on organizational practices for the recovery of hotel operations after a decline in tourist flows. Scientists Y. Zabaldina and I. Dvorska [13] analyze transformation processes in the tourism sector of Ukraine by implementing international practices. Author T. M. Petruk [14] considers management models for ensuring the stability of hotel enterprises during the pandemic. Further research should be directed towards developing adaptive practices for enterprises focused on long-term stability.

The fourth direction focuses on international experience and its adaptation to Ukrainian realities. Scientists E. Sidorova, O. Dniprov, M. Yunina, L. Bobrishova, and K. Mkrtchian [15] investigate the administrative and legal principles of public control over the implementation of state policy in the humanitarian sphere, focusing on crisis management in the hotel business. Prospects for further research in this direction lie in the study of transnational practices of anti-crisis management and their adaptation to the conditions of post-crisis recovery in Ukraine.

Thus, the research indicates the need for further improvement of methodological practices for assessing the effectiveness of forecasting strategies, adapting international experience to Ukrainian realities, and developing management models that can take into account military risks and economic fluctuations.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the general problem.

Despite the active study of forecasting methods as a tool for anti-crisis management, the issues of developing adaptive scenarios for the hotel business in Ukraine that consider specific risks associated with seasonality of demand, the impact of military operations, and the instability of consumer behavior remain unresolved. The lack of comprehensive criteria for assessing the effectiveness of management strategies, which consider not only financial indicators but also operational stability and changes in client segments, limits the possibilities of monitoring the implementation of management decisions in crisis conditions. The study aims to develop adaptive

practices for hotel enterprises in Ukraine, which face specific threats, particularly fluctuations in demand, the impact of military operations, and changes in consumer behavior. Determining criteria for assessing the effectiveness of management models, focused not only on financial indicators but also on operational stability, will allow for a comprehensive assessment of the impact of external factors on the activities of enterprises and provide a sound basis for decision-making.

Formulation of the objectives of the article (definition of tasks). The article aims to develop scientifically based practices for implementing scenario planning as a tool for anti-crisis management of hotel enterprises in Ukraine, taking into account modern challenges and risks.

To achieve the goal of the study, the following tasks were formulated:

1. To identify the methodological foundations of scenario planning for anti-crisis management of hotel enterprises and analyze their practical application in conditions of economic instability.

2. To investigate the risk aspects that affect the stability of hotel enterprises in Ukraine in crisis conditions, and to substantiate the criteria for assessing the effectiveness of scenario planning.

3. To develop recommendations for adapting scenario planning to the specifics of the Ukrainian hotel services market, considering the identified risks and management constraints.

Presentation of the primary material of the study. Scenario planning is one of the leading tools of anti-crisis management, which allows you to structure possible scenarios and make informed decisions based on forecasting risks and opportunities.

The methodological principles of scenario planning are based on a systematic analysis of the external and internal environment of the enterprise, identifying the main factors of influence, forming strategic alternatives, and assessing their consequences for the activities of hotel enterprises. In the context of anti-crisis management, scenario planning contributes not only to predicting potential crises

but also to adapting management decisions, taking into account possible changes in the market environment. Modern scenario planning methods include qualitative and quantitative indicators that provide a comprehensive analysis of situations and an assessment of their impact on the operational activities of the enterprise (table 1).

Table 1

Methodological components of scenario planning in anti-crisis management of hotel enterprises

Component	Content	Application in anti-crisis management
Identification of the main factors	Analysis of macroeconomic, political, social, and technological changes that may affect the hotel business	Identification of risks for forecasting crises
Scenario development	Creating several scenarios of events that differ in risk level and probability of implementation	Developing strategic alternatives to minimize the impact of crises
Evaluating scenarios	Analysis of the consequences of implementing each scenario for the financial and operational indicators of the enterprise	Determining priority measures to ensure sustainability
Choosing the optimal scenario	Choosing a scenario taking into account the resource capabilities of the enterprise and the level of risks	Implementing an adaptive anti-crisis management strategy
Monitoring and adjustment	Continuous monitoring of the implementation of the selected scenario and adaptation of the strategy in case of changes in the situation	Ensuring flexibility of management decisions in conditions of uncertainty

Source: based on [3, p. 74-75; 4, p. 251-253; 5, p. 498; 6, p.41; 7, p. 1578]

The components of scenario planning in the anti-crisis management of hotel enterprises provide a comprehensive practice of assessing potential threats and developing adaptive management solutions. Identifying the main risk components includes an analysis of macroeconomic changes, political instability, and social

transformations that may affect the activities of hotels. In particular, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the main risks were decreased tourist flows and increased sanitary measures' costs.

Scenario formation involves developing several alternatives for the development of events, varying in terms of risk level and probability of implementation. During military operations, management practices contribute to predicting the target audience's shift to the domestic market and a change in pricing policy to attract corporate clients.

The scenario assessment applied an analysis of the impact on financial indicators and operating costs, using quantitative forecasting methods: in the event of a significant decrease in income, it is advisable to adjust the cost structure and optimize personnel policy [8, p. 732].

The optimal scenario depends on the company's resilience to external challenges and resource capabilities. Depending on the conditions, practical measures can be taken, such as reformatting the marketing strategy, focusing on long-term room rental, or developing special service packages.

Monitoring and adjusting implemented scenarios ensure flexibility of management decisions and adaptation to changes in the market environment. The modern hotel business is transformed by implementing systems for monitoring financial indicators, receiving customer feedback, and forecasting demand dynamics. The stability of hotel enterprises in crisis conditions largely depends on the ability to identify and manage the main risks that may negatively affect their activities. In conditions of economic instability, martial law, and global crises, the hotel business faces risks caused by both internal and external factors. External risks include economic fluctuations, changes in consumer behavior, labor market instability, and exchange rate fluctuations. Internal risks are associated with imperfect management decisions, lack of crisis strategies, weak adaptability of the business model to new conditions, and a decrease in the quality of service. Timely

identification of key risks is essential for developing effective anti-crisis strategies and forming a sustainable management system (Table 2).

In 2022, with the introduction of martial law in the western regions of Ukraine, a record demand for hotel services was recorded due to the mass evacuation of the population from zones of active hostilities, which caused a sharp increase in tourist revenue. However, already in May-June, this indicator began to decline rapidly, making revising anti-crisis management strategies in the hotel business relevant [2]. The main risk factors were several aspects simultaneously, which increased their negative impact on the enterprise's sustainability. Economic risks, in particular, rising inflation and a decrease in the population's purchasing power, lead to a reduction in tourist flows and, accordingly, a decrease in hotel revenues. In addition, social challenges associated with changing consumer preferences require prompt adaptation of marketing strategies aimed at attracting new customer segments.

Table 2

Primary risk factors for hotel enterprises in Ukraine

Type of risk	Contents	Consequences
Economic	Fluctuations in demand, inflation, and rising resource costs	Decrease in income, increase in operating costs
Social	Changing consumer preferences, outflow of qualified personnel	Reduction in the client base, personnel losses
Political	Military actions, changes in legislation, and tax changes	Interruptions in operations, additional costs
Technological	Outdated IT systems, cyberattacks, and a lack of digital tools	Data loss, reduced efficiency of operations
Operational	Supply chain failure, deterioration in service quality	Disruption of operational processes, loss of customer loyalty

Source: based on [2; 7, p. 1580; 8, p. 734; 11, p. 8; 13, p. 125]

Political risks in hostilities are particularly relevant for Ukrainian hotels, as disruptions in the supply of resources, partial loss of tourist markets, and the need to comply with new legislative requirements can significantly complicate the

operational activities of enterprises. Such risks require the development of comprehensive crisis scenarios that cover not only adaptation to market changes, but also cost optimization and increased security of hotel infrastructure. At the same time, technological risks are significant in modern conditions, since implementing digital solutions in management processes can reduce costs and increase competitiveness [3, p. 76]. The lack of modern IT systems and the low level of employees' digital literacy can hinder the implementation of such initiatives.

In conditions of market instability and the growth of crisis phenomena in the hotel sector of Ukraine, the effectiveness of scenario planning is determined by the ability of this model to provide a timely response to risks, minimize the negative impact of external and internal factors, and maintain the operational stability of the enterprise. The assessment of the effectiveness of scenario planning is based on using criteria that allow for quantitatively and qualitatively determining the degree of compliance of the selected scenarios with the real conditions of the hotel enterprises. They cover both strategic and tactical levels of management, contributing to the development of adaptive models of response to crises (Table 3).

Table 3

Criteria for assessing the effectiveness of scenario planning by
hotel enterprises

Criteria	Content	Impact on anti-crisis management
Responsiveness	Speed of making management decisions within the framework of implementing the selected scenario	Reduction of losses through timely response
Flexibility of planning	Ability of the model to adjust depending on changes in the external environment	Reduction of the impact of unforeseen circumstances
Complexity of scenarios	Taking into account all possible risks and their consequences for the enterprise's activities	Increasing the accuracy of forecasts and stability of activities

Resource adaptability	The ability of the scenario to optimize the use of resources, taking into account crisis conditions	Reducing costs and maintaining competitive advantages
Implementability	Realism of scenario implementation, taking into account available resources and management capabilities	Increasing the level of implementation of plans and effectiveness

Source: based on [6, p. 42; 9, p. 179]

Analysis of the criteria for assessing the effectiveness of scenario planning allows us to identify the main aspects that ensure the resilience of organizations to crisis events. For the hotel business, the promptness of response to changes in the external environment minimizes the negative impact of unforeseen circumstances, ensuring timely adaptation to new conditions. Planning flexibility is a tool that provides the ability to make adjustments to the selected scenarios depending on current market trends. The complexity of the scenarios helps to increase the accuracy of forecasting possible risks and their impact on the operational activities of the enterprise.

An example of successful application of resource adaptability is the implementation of the LMS Collaborator online platform by Reikartz Hotel Group for personnel retraining and automation of the learning process. This solution reduced the costs of training new employees and increased the overall level of customer service by unifying service quality standards. In addition, implementing a system of regular online courses contributed to maintaining corporate culture during military operations, which guaranteed the stability of the company's operational activities [16].

Although scenario planning in hotel management is a promising tool for assessing potential threats and developing models for responding to unforeseen situations, its implementation faces several problems that reduce overall efficiency and complicate implementing complex management decisions. One of the main

obstacles is the lack of systematic methodological practices for forming forecast scenarios taking into account the specifics of the hotel business, which prevents the identification of the main risk factors and assessment of their impact on the operational activities of the enterprise [11, p. 11].

In addition, the insufficient integration of modern analytical tools and technologies into the scenario planning process is a significant obstacle to its practical application. Most hotel enterprises do not have access to current data on market trends, changes in consumer behavior, and economic fluctuations, which hinders the forecasting of scenarios for the development of crisis situations [9, p. 190]. The lack of automated data collection and processing systems limits the ability to respond on time to unforeseen changes and reduces the efficiency of management decisions.

Another challenge for hotel enterprises in crisis conditions is the difficulty of developing scenarios focused on the long-term perspective. The instability of the economic environment, constant changes in the legislative framework, and uncertainty about restoring tourist flows negatively affect the formation of alternative scenarios that consider various combinations of risks [4, p. 259]. Under conditions of limited resources, enterprises are forced to choose the most likely development scenarios, ignoring potential threats that may arise in the future.

Insufficient management personnel training in scenario planning is an additional limitation for its implementation. The lack of skills in strategic forecasting, data analysis, and assessment of the impact of risks on financial indicators leads to superficial development of scenarios. It limits the ability to respond to crises flexibly [4, p. 258]. These shortcomings complicate the process of making management decisions based on incomplete or outdated information, particularly reducing the overall effectiveness of anti-crisis management.

In addition, hotel enterprises' weak resource base (limited financial opportunities for investing in modern IT solutions and forecasting systems) is a serious obstacle to implementing the predicted changes [5, p. 499]. During a crisis,

enterprises often focus on short-term measures to preserve current assets, ignoring the need to form long-term strategies, which reduces their ability to adapt and effectively respond to unforeseen circumstances.

Implementing scenario planning for hotel enterprises in the Ukrainian market requires integrating comprehensive practices to ensure resilience to crisis phenomena and increasing the flexibility of management decisions. Given the specifics of the hotel business in Ukraine (unstable economic situation, the impact of military operations, fluctuations in tourist flows), it is advisable to develop recommendations that consider both strategic and operational aspects of the enterprises' activities.

The first stage of applying predictive techniques is to develop models emphasizing regional risks and the characteristics of target customer segments. In particular, it is advisable to identify possible scenarios for enterprises close to combat zones, regions with a high concentration of internally displaced persons, and resort areas that can potentially resume their activities after the situation stabilizes. This will allow you to focus on different groups of consumers, in particular, corporate clients, domestic tourists, and long-term rentals.

The second important area of adaptation is integrating digital tools for data collection and analysis, which will allow you to form more accurate forecasts and respond to market changes promptly. Using consumer behavior monitoring systems, demand analysis platforms, and loyalty programs will help reduce uncertainty and develop flexible response scenarios. In particular, implementing a CRM system that can segment the customer base and forecast demand can quickly adjust marketing strategies and implement pricing policies depending on current market conditions.

The third step is to optimize the resource base of hotel enterprises, emphasizing reducing costs and increasing management efficiency. This involves developing models focused on using energy-efficient technologies, reducing utility costs, and rationalizing the use of the room stock. To overcome the crisis, it is essential to consider possible options for lowering hotel occupancy and develop

strategies for repurposing individual facilities for long-term lease or use for corporate needs.

The fourth stage is to improve the personnel management system by developing various options for adapting human resources to new working conditions: retraining employees, introducing flexible work schedules, and creating a personnel reserve to fill key positions quickly in case of force majeure. In particular, it is advisable to develop specialized online courses for managers in risk and crisis management, which will increase their qualifications and adaptability to change.

The final stage is implementing a system of continuous risk monitoring using analytical tools to assess scenarios and adjust management decisions. In this context, creating a single information platform for collecting data on changes in consumer behavior, economic trends, and regulatory restrictions is advisable. This will contribute to the timely updating of response scenarios, adaptation of business processes, and reduction of the negative impact of crisis phenomena on the operational activities of hotel enterprises.

Thus, recommendations for adapting predictive planning in the Ukrainian market should be based on the integration of regionally oriented scenarios, the implementation of digital tools for data collection and analysis, optimization of the resource base, development of human resources, and the creation of a system of continuous risk monitoring. Compliance with these recommendations will guarantee the resilience of hotel enterprises to crisis phenomena and increase their competitiveness in the post-crisis period.

Conclusions. As a result of the study, it was found that the main advantages of scenario planning are the ability to model different scenarios, assess their potential impact on the operational activities of the enterprise, and form adaptive management decisions. However, several problems were identified that complicate the practical application of scenario planning in the Ukrainian hotel sector. Among the main issues identified were insufficient methodological development of scenario

formation practices taking into account industry specifics, a low level of integration of digital tools for data collection and analysis, a lack of qualified specialists in the development of strategic scenarios, and limited financial resources for the implementation of modern IT solutions.

Recommendations for adapting scenario planning for hotel enterprises, taking into account Ukrainian specifics, include the phased integration of digital analytical platforms for collecting data on market trends and consumer behavior, the development of specialized courses for management personnel on strategic forecasting and crisis management techniques, the implementation of flexible crisis response scenarios with an emphasis on adapting to internal and external threats, in particular, the creation of a single information system for coordinating management decisions and monitoring the results of scenario implementation. Prospects for further research include the development of methods for quantitatively assessing the effectiveness of scenario planning, the integration of machine learning algorithms for predicting risks in the hotel business, and the study of international experience in adapting scenario planning to economic instability and crisis phenomena.

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